

DEEP LEARNING FOR MODELING OF MULTISCALE FLOW PHENOMENA IN COMPOSITES MANUFACTURING

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Abstract

Manufacturing fiber-reinforced composites (FRCs) with fast and efficient resin infusion processes, such as resin transfer molding (RTM), involves impregnating a fabric with a polymer resin. Fabrics typically exhibit a multimodal pore distribution defined by the pores between fibers (in a yarn) and the pores between yarns (in the fabrics or, more broadly, in the preforms). This multimodal pore distribution and the relative orientation of individual layers in a layup necessitate a complete understanding of multiscale flow phenomena to ensure high-quality manufacturing in reasonable cycle times. In addition, the identification of the permeability tensor is required for predicting the flow patterns and the fill times[1]. In contrast, air entrapment due to the interplay of capillary and viscous effects at the flow front needs to be well understood to predict the residual voids in composites and mitigate them [2].

Addressing the flow-related issues has called for the development of numerical algorithms to predict the permeability tensor of fabric unit cells, to identify the processing conditions leading to void formation and transport, to optimize the mold design by taking into account the variable nature of fabrics, and by accounting for tool interaction leading to over/under-compacted areas. However, computationally expensive simulations are required for modeling the manufacturing of FRCs. The influence of smaller scales is often overlooked or oversimplified through homogenization in favor of computational times [3]. The accuracy of these simulations degrades significantly when considering both geometrical variability (e.g., corners, over/under-compaction areas) or material variability (e.g., ply drop-off, multi-material layups). Thus, the flow patterns and residual voids become challenging to predict in practical applications. To address this issue, we are developing a bottom-up approach from the fiber scale to propose a machine learning-accelerated and computationally efficient framework to account for the uncertainties and variations originating at all relevant scales and their convoluted impact on both FRCs manufacturing and the end products' lifetime.

Figure 1 outlines our approach to developing computationally efficient models for predicting the flow phenomena at micro- and meso-scale. This entails 1- a convolutional neural network (CNN) based algorithm to predict the permeability of 3D fibrous microstructures by treating them as a series of 2D slices along the fiber direction and 2- an encoder-decoder neural network to propose a probabilistic tool for localizing the areas in representative geometries within a fabric layup that are prone to void formation under different processing conditions. Our approach based on using deep learning algorithms provides accurate predictions and a significant reduction in computational times. These performances are exemplified by more than 80% of individual permeability predictions from an unseen dataset having less than 20% deviation from the baseline values obtained via physics-based flow simulations and by the computational time being on the order of a few seconds in comparison to several hours as we visually summarized in Figure 2 and have explained in detail in [4].

During the talk, we will detail the transverse permeability prediction pipeline, including the microstructure generation, flow simulations to generate the data used for training and validating the deep learning algorithm, and assessment of predictive capabilities of CNN in 2D and 3D scenarios with different datasets. We will also present the capabilities of encoder-decoder neural networks for predicting the residual voids in representative geometries characteristic of woven fabrics.

Figure 1. An overview of our activities on for AI based prediction of multiscale flow phenomena in composite manufacturing

Figure 2. a) CNN architecture we used in ref [4]. b) CNN predictions vs. physics-based simulation results for permeability

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References

- [1] Zeng X, Endruweit A, Brown LP, Long AC. Numerical prediction of in-plane permeability for multilayer woven fabrics with manufacture-induced deformation. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2015;77:266–74.
- [2] Teixidó H, Staal J, Caglar B, Michaud V. Capillary Effects in Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite Processing: A Review. *Front Mater* 2022;9:1–24.
- [3] Karaki M, Younes R, Trochu F, Lafon P. Progress in Experimental and Theoretical Evaluation Methods for Textile Permeability 2019.
- [4] Caglar B, Broggi G, Ali MA, Orgéas L, Michaud V. Deep learning accelerated prediction of the permeability of fibrous microstructures. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2022;158.